

PROCESSING AND PROPERTIES OF PULTRUDED FIBER REINFORCED
POLYMETHYL METHACRYLATE COMPOSITES (II)

CHEN-CHI M. MA AND CHIN-HSING CHEN

INSTITUTE OF CHEMICAL ENGINEERING
NATIONAL TSING HUA UNIVERSITY
HSIN-CHU, TAIWAN, R.O.C. 30043

ABSTRACT

A novel process has been developed to manufacture polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA) pultruded composites. Processing parameters including MMA prepolymer preparation, die temperature and dynamic mechanical properties of PMMA composites are investigated.

From DSC diagram and the molecular weight of PMMA that the optimum die temperature were found. A dynamic mechanical test method was used to determine the damping behaviour across a temperature range. From mechanical and thermal properties studies it was found that PMMA pultruded composites show excellent properties.

Key words: Pultrusion, PMMA, glass, carbon, Kevlar^R fiber, composites, properties.

I. INTRODUCTION

Pultrusion process has been grown very rapidly in the past

decades due to the development of materials and processing technique [1]. However, the pultrusion process has been associated almost exclusively with thermoset polymers such as unsaturated polyester, vinyl ester, phenolic and epoxy resin [2-4] from the early 1950's. Material handling of thermoset materials is very tedious since these materials inherent a limited shelf life and are often stored at very low temperature. Quality control is another cost factor to thermoset resin since each batch from manufacturer must be inspected before mixing and each formulation must be matched with previous batches [5]. Consequently, composite fabricators are searching thermoplastic matrix materials as replacements.

Thermoplastic materials show the potential applications in high-speed, low tooling cost, and short cycle time process. Substantial cost reductions can also be realized due to their unlimited shelf life, reduced scrap and waste (due to the recyclability of the material), ease of repair and ability to be welded or fused together [6-10]. Thermoplastic composite material provides the opportunity for developing an entirely new area of pultruded composite profiles and structures [11].

In this study, polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA) thermoplastic pultrusion was investigated. Methyl methacrylate monomer was used directly and polymerized in the die. It provides a new concept for in-situ thermoplastic pultrusion [12]. This paper presents the preparation of PMMA prepolymer for pultrusion, optimum die temperatures and dynamic mechanical properties of pultruded fiber reinforced PMMA composites.

II. EXPERIMENTAL

1. Materials

Table 1 summarizes the materials used in this study which include methyl methacrylate monomer, initiator, glass fiber, carbon fiber, Kevlar^R fiber and MMA prepolymer synthesized in this study.

2. Preparation of MMA prepolymer

In this study, the methyl methacrylate prepolymer was synthesized by heating the inhibitor-free monomer in a water bath at 55 °C until it became noticeably. In order to remove the reaction heat, the synthesized prepolymer was immersed in an ice bath for 30 min, then was stored at low temperature. The viscosity of MMA prepolymer was measured by a Brookfield viscometer as shown in Figure 1. An optimum temperature at 55 °C was found. When the temperature is lower than 55 °C, processing time will be too long, however, when temperature is high than 55 °C, the viscosity of MMA prepolymer can not be controlled easily.

3. Apparatus

- (1) A pultrusion die with multiple heating zone of dimensions of 0.319 x 1.27 x 82.0 cm (thickness x width x length), was custom-designed. The surfaces of the stainless steel die have been treated by chrome plating.
- (2) Viscosities were measured with a Brookfield viscometer model RVF during the synthesis of MMA prepolymer.
- (3) Universal material testing machine: (a) HT-8501, Horng Dar Co., Taiwan, R.O.C (b) Instron 1123, Instron Co., U.S.A. (c) Shimadzu Autograph Co., Japan.
- (4) Impact strength testing machine : TMI-43-1, Testing Machine Inc., U.S.A.
- (5) GPC (Gel Permeation Chromatography) : Unical 3-02, Viscotek Co., U.S.A.
- (6) DSC (Differential Scanning Calorimetry) : Model 910, Du Pont Co., U.S.A.
- (7) RDS (Rheometric Dynamic Spectrometer) : Model 800, Rheometrics Inc., U.S.A.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Die Temperature

The operating die temperature was determined by a differential scanning calorimetry (DSC). Five to ten milligrams of MMA prepolymer sample was placed on a DSC cell. Both the isothermal scanning at 120 °C, 130 °C, 140 °C, 150 °C and the dynamic scanning at 10 °C/min were conducted. From the

DSC results as shown in Figure 2 , it was found that the exothermic peak reached a maximum at 144.03 °C and the total heat generated during the polymerization is 462.2 J/g. The result of isothermal scanning test is shown in Figure 3, these DSC curves summarized the comparison of four processing temperatures, from which the polymerization rate (time) can be obtained. When the temperatures were set at 120 °C, 130°C, 140°C and 150°C, the exothermic peaks reached the maximum at 2.7min, 2.2 min, 1.5 min and 0.5 min, respectively, results indicate that the higher the temperature, the faster the polymerization rate. One can observe the suitable die temperature range in this study is between 140 °C and 180 °C. The die temperature can not be lower than 140 °C, otherwise the composites can not be processed in a short time (48-120 sec) in the die , and it shall not be higher than 180 °C, or the molecular weight will be decreased sharply. When the die temperature were set at 140 °C, 160 °C, 180 °C and 200 °C, the number average molecular weights of PMMA were 53,000-55,000 , 30,000-32,000 , 17,000-19,000 and 9,000-11,000, respectively at the pulling rate of 40 cm/min.

2.Dynamic Mechanical Properties

The dynamic mechanical properties of various pultruded composites are illustrated in Figure 4. Effect of pulling rate on the dynamic mechanical properties of pultruded PMMA/GF composites are shown in Figures 5 and 6. From Figure 4, one can observe that the dynamic shear storage modulus (G') of the pultruded glass fiber reinforced PMMA composites are higher than those of pultruded Nylon 6 and unsaturated polyester composites [13]. When the temperature is over glass transition (T_g) of PMMA, the storage modulus of pultruded PMMA composites decreased sharply, but the pultruded Nylon 6 and unsaturated polyester composites decreased smoothly. As can be seen in Figures 5 and 6 that the dynamic shear storage modulus(G') and dynamic shear loss modulus(G'') increased with the decreasing pulling rate, since the conversion of polymer and wetting out of fibers by PMMA resin at low pulling rate were more completed, and the weight average molecular weight increased with decreasing pulling rate.

3. Fracture Behavior

The appearances of the fracture surface of tensile test specimens are shown in Figure 7. The pultruded GF/PMMA composites show poor interfacial bonding between matrix and fiber since the elongation of PMMA matrix (3%) is smaller than that of glass fiber (4%). However, the pultruded CF/PMMA and KF/PMMA composites show the breaking of fiber due to carbon and Kevlar^R fiber break before PMMA matrix. The elongations of the carbon fiber (1.52%) and Kevlar^R (2.5%) are smaller than that of PMMA matrix.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

A feasibility study of methyl methacrylate resin for pultrusion process has been conducted. From DSC diagrams and the weight average molecular weight that the suitable pultrusion die temperature is in the range of 140 °C to 180 °C.

The dynamic mechanical properties explicit the dynamic shear storage moduli (G') of the PMMA pultruded composites are higher than those of pultruded nylon 6 and unsaturated polyester composites. When the temperature is over T_g , the storage modulus of pultruded PMMA composites decreased sharply, but the pultruded Nylon 6 and unsaturated polyester composites decreased smoothly. The dynamic storage modulus (G') and dynamic shear loss modulus (G'') of pultruded fiber reinforced PMMA composites increased with decreasing pulling rate.

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Table 1. Materials Used for This Study

Material	Specification	Supplier
Monomer	Methyl methacrylate (Purified industry grade)	Kaohsiung Monomer Co., Taiwan, R.O.C.
Resin	MMA prepolymer (Mw=1,200)	Synthesized in this study
Initiator	Benzoyl peroxide(BPO) (Guaranteed reagent)	Kanto Chemical Co., Japan
Fiber	Glass fiber(E-glass) 764-NT-218 Diameter=13.1 μm	PPG Co., U.S.A.
	Carbon fiber,HT-12000 Diameter=7.0 μm	Toho Co., Japan
	Kevlar fiber, K-49 Diameter=11.9 μm	DuPont Co., U.S.A.

Figure 1. Viscosity of Synthesized MMA Prepolymer at Various Temperature.

Figure 2. DSC Thermograms of MMA Prepolymer by Dynamic Scanning at 10 °C/min.

Figure 3. DSC Thermograms of MMA Prepolymer by Isothermal Scanning at : (—) 120 °C (---) 130 °C (.....) 140 °C (— · —) 150 °C.

Figure 4. Dynamic Shear Storage Modulus (G') vs. Temperature of Various Pultruded Composites : (—) PMMA (---) Nylon 6 (— · —) Polyester.

Figure 5. Dynamic Shear Storage Modulus (G') of Pultruded GF/PMMA Composites at Various Pulling Rates : (—) 20 cm/min (---) 40 cm/min (-·-) 70 cm/min (····) 100 cm/min.

Figure 6. Dynamic Shear Loss Modulus (G'') of Pultruded GF/PMMA Composite at various Pulling Rates : (—) 20 cm/min (---) 40 cm/min (-·-) 70 cm/min (····) 100 cm/min.

(a) Before Test

(b) After Test

Figure 7. Tensile Test Sample of Pultruded Fiber Reinforced PMMA Composites. (a) Before Test (b) After Test.